

The Effect of Transformational Leadership, Organizational Culture Through Job Satisfaction and Job Motivation on Employee Performance (Case PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Sugar Takalar Factory)

Abd.Muis,¹ Siti Haerani,² Muhammad Idrus Taba³

¹Abd.Muis Master in Management Science, Faculty of Economics and Business, Hasanuddin University

² Siti Haerani Lecturers, Faculty of Economics and Business, Hasanuddin University

³ Muhammad Idrus Taba Lecturers, Faculty of Economics and Business, Hasanuddin University

Abstract:- This study aims to determine the application of transformational leadership, organizational culture, job satisfaction, work motivation and employee performance contained in PT. Nusantara Plantation XIV Takalar Sugar Factory. This research is quantitative approach, by This type of research is survey in nature, namely analyzing facts and data that support the information needed to support research discussions. The data obtained are subsequently processed in the form of a narrative or text, then presented in a descriptive form. The results of this study explained that the transformational leadership of organizational culture, job satisfaction, work motivation and employee performance contained in PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory has not been able to apply properly, it can be proven by the inability of the leadership to increase self-confidence and motivate them to work beyond their work, as well as the frequent delays in work, not making good use of free time, not being able to complete tasks assigned by superiors, not on time, often being apathetic to the regulations that have been set, low levels of employee cooperation with their work, low level of achievement of the quality of work results with predetermined targets, and accuracy in carrying out work in terms of work results that are still incomplete, and lack of employee initiative to carry out tasks. As well as there is still a delay in completing the assigned tasks. However, leaders are expected to be able to maintain good communication with employees so that the company will improve and develop as expected by the company.

Keywords:- Transformational leadership, organizational culture, job satisfaction, work motivation and employee performance contained in PT. Nusantara Plantation XIV Takalar Sugar Factory.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of human resources and business competition have their own challenges in facing the era of Society 5.0 new era or new normal order with the COVID-19 outbreak which has now hit all parts of the world has had a significant impact on all sectors of business life, business, as well as those felt by SOE businesses. However, soe businesses must not stop engaged in running a business and must be proactive about these changes so that they can survive to develop, and advance. By having employees who are qualified and have integrity. In this case, employees are emphasized to perform the tasks that have been assigned to them professionally, work hard, discipline, honesty, high loyalty and full of dedication to success in each of their work Hamid et al., (2003).

State-Owned Enterprises, in this study are PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory, is a company engaged in the plantation sector. In making improvements to competitive advantages, it is required to make continuous improvements (Continuous Improvement). PT. Nusantara Plantation XIV Takalar Sugar Factory must be flexible and provide maximum service. PT. Nusantara Plantation XIV Takalar Sugar Factory must be managed professionally and optimally because if it is not managed professionally, it will not be able to compete by other similar companies, so losses and setbacks will be experienced by PT. Nusantara Plantation XIV Takalar Sugar Factory.

State-Owned Enterprises, in this study is PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory, is a company engaged in the plantation sector. In improving competitive advantage, it is required to make continuous improvements (Continuous Improvement). PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory must be flexible and provide maximum service. PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory must be managed professionally and maximally because if it is not managed professionally it will not be able to compete with other similar companies, so that losses and setbacks will be experienced by PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory.

PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory has quite a number of permanent employees, namely in 2020 - 2021 it reaches 142 employees, of which 17 are management employees and another 125 are implementing employees. In 2020 - 2021 the number of permanent employees at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV Takalar Sugar Factory for the last 2 years has not changed.

G. R. Terry (2010) gives the opinion that management is a process consisting of planning, organizing, mobilizing and controlling actions to set and achieve goals through the use of human resources and other resources. Handoko (2009) provides a definition that management is a process of planning, organizing, directing, and supervising the efforts of organizational members and the use of other organizational resources to achieve predetermined organizational goals. Meanwhile, Hasibuan (2013), provides a definition that management is a science and art in managing and utilizing human resources and other resources to the fullest. based on some of these understandings, it can be concluded that management is a process of planning, organizing, controlling, and supervising to achieve the goals that have been set optimally and efficiently.

Transformational leadership can be described as a figure who can provide a stimulus to followers to change their motives, beliefs, values, and abilities so that the followers' personal interests and goals are in line with the company's organizational vision. Burns, (1978) Bass, (1985).

Rotwell, Stavros, and Sullivan (2015), provide a definition that transformational leadership is a leadership style that can change followers to overcome personal interests and provide challenges to achieve corporate goals together. Transformational leadership has a strong self-identification link, creating a relevant new vision for the future of the company and the relationship between leader and followers is based on something more than satisfactory compliance. Transformational leaders are defined as a need for change, creating a new vision, which can be used to mobilize commitment to carrying out the vision and be able to change followers both individually and in teams.

Robbins and Judge (2014), provide a definition that organizational culture is a system of shared meanings followed by members that can distinguish an organization from other organizations. Ivancevich (et. al.) (2007), provides a definition that organizational culture is something followers feel and how to interpret it can provide a pattern of beliefs, values, and expectations to followers.

Motivation can be interpreted as a concept that can be described by the forces that exist within the employee that can be initiated and directed through the person's behavior. Motivation can also be interpreted as a driver for someone to make a maximum contribution to the success of organizational goals (Siagian, 2016). The word motivation comes from the Latin *movere* which means to move. In the current context, motivation is a psychological process that can lead to the stimulus and persistence of an activity that is sincerely directed at a goal (Kreitner and Kinicki, 2014).

Yukl (2013), job satisfaction is employees' feelings about their work resulting from the evaluation process of various aspects of work, such as pleasant and unpleasant work experiences and employee expectations of future work experiences.

II. METHODS

The approach in this study uses a quantitative approach. This type of research is survey in nature, namely by analyzing facts and data that can support the information needed so that it can support research discussions, in solving and providing solutions to the main problems proposed by using an analytical observational design with a cross sectional approach Creswel (2015). In cross sectional research, researchers only observe phenomena at certain points in time (Hemed 2015), this approach is used to see the relationship between one variable and another.

III. RESULT

Transformational leadership can have a direct influence on job satisfaction, these results indicate that the transformational leadership of PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory still needs to improve and pay attention to the leadership style applied to employees, because the leadership at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory, is able to influence employee job satisfaction. Organizational culture has a direct influence on employees' work motivation, this shows that the more maximally the company's organizational culture is applied and obeyed, the higher the employee's work motivation. Job satisfaction has a direct effect on work motivation, this shows that the higher the job satisfaction, the higher the employee's work motivation. The results of this study indicate that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance. The close influence of work motivation on employee performance must receive special attention management. Because good employee performance can also be wrong one factor increasing the company's performance PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory.

IV. DISCUSSION

Transformational leadership has a direct influence on job satisfaction, from these results it can be seen that the leadership of PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory needs to be improved and continue to pay attention to the leadership style applied to employees at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory, has a dominant influence on employee job satisfaction. Organizational culture has a direct influence on employee motivation, this shows that if the organizational culture in the company is getting better and carried out optimally by employees. Job satisfaction has a direct effect on work motivation, this shows that the more attention is paid to employee job satisfaction, the higher the employee's work motivation.

Based on the results of this study indicate that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance. Work motivation has a close influence on employee performance and must receive special attention from the leadership. Because good employee performance is also one of the factors to increase the company's performance, PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, which has been described previously explains that the variables of leadership and work motivation have a positive effect on employee performance. The magnitude of the influence of leadership and work motivation on employee performance is 61.4% obtained from the analysis of the determinant coefficient (R Square). the remaining 29.6% which is influenced by other factors not examined. For example, morale, organizational culture and others. This means that the variables of leadership and work motivation have a strong relationship with the performance variable.

in this regard, employee performance is at its lowest point when there are no independent variables that affect it. This means that leadership and work motivation as independent variables have a very important role in improving the performance of employees of PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory because employee performance will decline without leadership and work motivation to influence.

First, Transformational leadership has a significant effect on performance employee. However, this insignificant effect has an impact negative on work motivation, this is indicated by the attitude of Leaders/Directors, against employees who violate work regulations/rules, the leadership does not immediately give sanctions, new leaders give sanctions if they have been opposed by outstanding employees and will threaten the position they occupy, because the Leaders/Directors at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory also, cannot distinguish between employees who excel and employees who do not excel, so that employees who have excelled at the company feel that their performance is not appreciated, then interpret the work discipline of employees, leaders/directors, translate work discipline that is employees show high levels of loyalty as a manifestation of subordinates' loyalty to the company, when in fact work discipline is based on fear or simply because employees are overshadowed by threats, even dismissal without the opportunity to defend themselves.

Second, work motivation has a significant influence on employee performance, with work motivation, employees will be more focused and focused on achieving company goals. Because of the description above, it is not surprising when the results of this study indicate that work motivation is the dominant factor in influencing employee performance improvement at PT. Plantation Nusanatara XIV (Persero) Takalar Sugar Factory.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Hemed M. Cross-sectional studies. Paper presented at: Training Course in Sexual and Reproductive Health Research; 2015 Nov 20; Geneva <https://www.gfmer.ch/SRH-Course-2015/research-methodology/Cross-sectional-studies-Hemed-2015.htm>.
- [2]. Burns, J.M., Bernardin, H.J. & Russel, J.E.A (1993). Human Resource Management an experiential approach. Singapore: Mc Graw-Hill, Inc.Leadership. New York: Harper and Row, 1978.
- [3]. Bass, B. M. Leadership and Performance. New York: Free Press, 1985..
- [4]. G.R. Terry. 2010. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Edisi Pertama. Cetakan Pertama. Jakarta : Penerbit Kencana.
- [5]. Handoko.T.Hani. Manajemen Personalialia dan Sumber Daya Manusia. Yogyakarta: BPFE Yogyakarta, 2001.
- [6]. Rotwell, Stavros dkk. Practicing Organization Development: Leading Transformational Change: Fourth Edition. Learning & Performance Systems, English: Wiley-Blackwell, 2015
- [7]. Robbins, Stephen P dan Timothy A Judge. 2014. Perilaku Organisasi. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [8]. Yukl. Kepemimpinan Dalam Organisasi. Jakata: PT.INDEKS, 2005